

AMIR HAYDAR - THE LUMINARY OF KNOWLEDGE AND SCIENCE
(BASED ON THE WORK "MAKTUBOTI AMIR HAYDAR")

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12217682>

Annotation: This article covers on the efforts of Amir Haydar, one of the rulers of Bukhara, to improve the life of society. Also, his letters on various issues are analyzed for their importance from the point of view of the era.

Key words: society, development, government, madrasa, dynasty, education, collection, patriotism, honor, knowledge, zakat.

Majority of rulers who have lived in history paid attention to science and patronized it in order to serve the development of their countries. In particular, among the rulers of various states that emerged on the territory of Uzbekistan, there are many rulers who fought for the development of science.

Among the representatives of the Mangit dynasty that ruled Bukhara, there were emirs who loved science and supported it and patronized it. As a vivid example of this, Amir Shahmurad (1741-1800) as soon as he became the ruler, revised the activities of all mosques and madrasas, which are the center of education and science in the country. He established foundation properties for them and strengthened their economic foundations. He also repaired the damaged ones and restarted them. He carried out monetary reform and increased the salaries of teachers, students, and scholars. He raised their value and position in society. Amir himself was a great scientist and taught several subjects at the Mir Arab Madrasah.

Later, his son Amir Haydar, who succeeded him, continued the work done by his father. After various military conflicts and campaigns, he also paid attention to the field of science. He appreciated scientists and respected them.

"Maktuboti Amir Haydar", which is the collection of correspondence of Amir Haidar with various officials and officials during the years of his reign, which is kept in the fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni. In it, we can see Amir Haydar's correspondence related to different fronts in different years.

In one letter of this letter, we can see the respect and attention of the emir to the scholars of his father's time. In the content of the letter, he expressed his respect for the old intellectual who has been serving the dynasty and the country since his father's time. The letter was as follows:

“The honorable figure deserving of respect in government, Muhammad Hakim Mehtar.

Let it be known with gratitude, in the spirit of royal benevolence, that Muhammad Musokhoja is regarded as one of our esteemed, veteran benefactors. According to the royal decree, you must duly provide him with the care and kindness required, considering his past services and his current situation. Stay informed about his condition and keep him informed in due time. Let the royal command be executed accordingly. Assalomu alaykum [1]”.

In another letter, we can witness Amir Haydar’s comments about the financial situation of the Higher Madrasa, the salaries of the teachers and the payment of the students’ stipends, and he showed the ways to solve the problem:

“Respected leader, holding a prestigious position in authority, a person of high esteem in the government, Muhammad Hakim Devonbegi.

Let it be known with gratitude that, enriched with honorable rewards, we allocate a stipend of one thousand from the zakat fund of our esteemed madrasa to the students of the Qur’an and seekers of knowledge every month. We had instructed you to also give them a small amount. However, the money we sent was insufficient. Therefore, they may not have been given less money, but rather they have not been given anything at all since one or two months.

We have devised a rule for this. Accordingly, if the zakat funds run out, we would borrow money from large-scale sources and pay the Qur’an custodians and seekers of knowledge at the esteemed madrasa. When the time for zakat comes, we would settle their accounts with the debts incurred. Now, you too should borrow money from large-scale sources and assign duties to the Qur’an students and seekers of knowledge at the esteemed madrasa. God willing, we will settle the accounts with them on time. Deliver the duties to the supervisor and make sure they receive them. Assalomu alaykum [2]”.

There are several letters in this collection of letters that leave no doubt that Amir Haydar was aware of the situation of every madrasa in the country. In one of these letters, we can see that Amir Haydar paid attention to the delay in providing the income that should be given to the Devonbegi madrasa from the waqf lands:

“To the honorable, esteemed, trustworthy figure of authority, Muhammad Hakim Devonbeg.

Let it be known with gratitude that, despite being enriched with generous blessings, some of the endowments related to Devonbegi Madrasa have not yet

been handed over. You must send the ungiven endowments to the custodian responsible for those places. Assalomu alaykum [3]”.

In another letter, we see his response to the application received by the Khorjin madrasa regarding the waqf lands and the way to solve the problem:

“Respected leader, Muhammad Hakim Mehtar, a trustworthy individual in the government.

Let it be known with gratitude that we have received your request regarding the endowment of the Khorjin Madrasa. If the endowment of the mentioned madrasa has been completed, please preserve it. Further details will be conveyed to you orally through Barot Oqsoqol. Assalomu alaykum[4]”.

In the letters, we not only find information related to issues concerning madrasas but also about acts of kindness extended to specific individuals within the madrasa. For example, in the following letter, it is mentioned that Amir Haydar has officially provided benefits to certain individuals at Oliy Madrasa through formal documents, supporting them economically and morally. Through this, we observe that there is a specific type of official document known as a “sanadi mehriboniy” (document regarding the provision of kindness), indicating that those who receive it are entitled to special privileges and assistance. The letter was as follows:

“Respected leader, possessing a high position in authority in the government affairs, a trusted individual of the government, Muhammad Hakim Mehtar.

Please be informed with gratitude that we have received your request sent to the higher authority.

We have issued documents regarding acts of kindness towards residents at the esteemed madrasa. Please provide them with their dues”[5].

In the “Maktuboti Amir Haydar”, such letters are precious, as they present historical records of the educational activities carried out by our ancestors for the younger generation, promoting patriotism, respect for values, and nurturing a sense of honor for history and ancestors.

References:

1. Abu Rayhon Beruniy nomidagi Sharqshunoslik instituti, № AR-5412, 32-maktub, 14 bet. Tarjimon: A.Boltayev.
2. Abu Rayhon Beruniy nomidagi Sharqshunoslik instituti, № AR-5412, 100-maktub, 43-44 betlar. Tarjimon: A.Boltayev.
3. Abu Rayhon Beruniy nomidagi Sharqshunoslik instituti, № AR-5412, 19-maktub, 9-10 betlar. Tarjimon: A.Boltayev.

4. Abu Rayhon Beruniy nomidagi Sharqshunoslik instituti, № AR-5412, 77-maktub, 33 bet. Tarjimon: A.Boltayev.
5. Abu Rayhon Beruniy nomidagi Sharqshunoslik instituti, № AR-5412, 110-maktub, 47-48- betlar. Tarjimon: A.Boltayev.
6. Sobirovich T. B. Evolution of ideas and views on the development of democratic society and spiritual renewals //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – №. 10. – C. 243-250.

